

**PSYCHOLOGIST IN EDUCATION: STUDY CARRIED OUT IN THE
MUNICIPALITY OF CEDRO-PE PURSUANT TO LAW 13.935/2019** DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8432200***Irismar Aparecida do Nascimento***

Effective teacher in the Municipality of Crato, degree in pedagogy (URCA) , participates in the Research Group on Education, Work and Teacher Training (GEPET)

irismar.nascimento@urca.br

Francisca Clara de Paula Oliveira

Associate Professor at the Regional University of Cariri -URCA. He has a degree in Pedagogy from the Federal University of Ceará (1990), a Master's degree in Education from the Federal University of Ceará (1996), a PhD in Education from the Federal University of São Carlos, SP (2005) and a post-doctorate in Public Policies and Human Training from the Postgraduate Program in Public Policies and Human Training (PPFH) at UERJ (2016). In management positions at URCA, she was coordinator of the Pedagogy Course (2005-2007),

Director of the Education Center of this HEI (2007-2011), local coordinator of the interinstitutional master's degree in Law (URCA/UNISC), and Institutional coordinator of PRODOCÊNCIA /CAPES (2010-2013). She is currently coordinator of the Group of Studies and Research in Education, Work and Teacher Training -GEPET (CNPq,2008), of the Structuring Teaching Center -NDE of the Pedagogy Course, of the Teacher Training Center-NFD, of Dinter in Education in a partnership URCA/UFRN and Institutional Coordinator of PIBID. As a research teacher, she investigates problems and themes related to education and work, teacher training, teaching work and educational policies. In the Pedagogy Course, he teaches the Introduction to the Pedagogy and Educational Policies Seminar subjects. She is a permanent professor of the Masters in Professional Education at URCA-MPEDU and an MEC evaluator in the area of Pedagogy. francisca.clara@urca.br

Márcia Kelma de Alencar Abreu

He has a degree in psychology from the federal university of ceará (2000), a degree in a special pedagogical training program from the state university of ceará (2003), and a master's degree in psychology from the federal university of ceará (2006) and a doctorate in

psychology from the federal university of ceará (2019). She is currently an adjunct professor at the State University of Ceará on the psychology course. has experience in the area of education, with an emphasis on social psychology, educational psychology and educational research , kelma.abreu@urca

ABSTRACT

This article has as its object of study the performance of psychologists in basic education from Law 13.935 of November 11, 2019, which provides for the presence of psychologists and social workers in public schools. The objective of this work is to understand and explain the ways in which the presence of the psychologist in the municipality of Cedro-PE has been effective. The methodology used was documentary and field research. The documentary research adopted as a starting point the Federal Constitution of 1988 in the articles that deal with education, the Law of Guidelines and Bases of Education (LDB) of 1996, the National Education Plan (PNE) of 2014 and the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC) of 2017 (BRAZIL, 2017). Law 13.935/2019 (BRASI, 2019), which provides for psychology and social worker services in public schools, Bill 3688/2000 (BRASIL, 2000). which preceded the above Law and the document prepared by the Federal Council of Psychology on performance in schools (2019). Semi-structured interviews were conducted with the Municipal Secretary of Education and the psychologist who serves the schools in the municipality. The reality perceived in the municipality of Cedro from the research carried out made evident the importance and need for psychologists in education. In this regard, one of the findings of the research is the identification of the social, cultural, economic and emotional aggravations caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, with a strong and solid impact on the functioning of the school and consequently on the entire school community. The research also revealed that social isolation was the preponderant factor for changing the habits and behaviors of students, teachers and families, which resulted in the emergence of many problems of a psycho-emotional nature in the school community. Thus, the resumption of face-to-face teaching after the COVID 19 pandemic became a major challenge for schools, making psychological support and support for students, teachers and families an essential action from then on. The effectiveness of Law 13.935/2019 is an urgent matter, so it is necessary to study, talk and above all charge the competent bodies for plans and actions that enable compliance with the aforementioned legislation. This study proposes to expose elements that indicate significant improvements in the social quality of education in the municipality of Cedro after compliance with the Law that made possible the mandatory presence of psychologists and social workers in public schools.

Keywords: English Language. Same formatting as the Summary in Portuguese.

CEDRO-PE: A SMALL MUNICIPALITY WITH A BIG CHALLENGE

This study's research object is the presence of psychologists in education based on Law 13,935 of November 11, 2019, which provides for the presence of psychologists and social workers in public schools. To deepen the investigation, we limited the study to the municipality of Cedro-PE, to find out how the presence and performance of these professionals has been in

this city. We seek to expose the importance and need for psychology in education, as well as present some indications of how professionals in this area can carry out their work in the educational field.

Through this study it will be possible to understand the mechanisms adopted by the Department of Education of the Municipality of Cedro - PE when they need to resort to the field of psychology and its professionals to support the school community. By addressing the issues, problems and principles that motivate this action, the aim was to open a range of reflections to educators and society in general about the challenges faced daily by public schools.

The investigation of the topic aimed to raise questions that problematize it, the aim is to develop an instrument that serves as direction and basis for educational practices. "It is about making the results of research known which, in turn, may generate reactions and contribute to the dynamics of awareness and eventually suggest the beginning of another cycle of action and investigation."(THIOLLENT , 1986, p.71)

The research was developed in the municipality of Cedro-PE through semi-structured interviews with the Municipal Department of Education and the psychologist who meets the municipality's demands. Our objective was to discover how the presence of psychologists in public schools in the city of Cedro-PE has been effective since Law 13,935/2019? This way, it will be possible to identify the forms adopted by the municipality in the face of situations that require the support of psychologists, and the human and technological resources necessary for this professional's work.

The present study seeks to address this topic taking into account the problems and challenges faced by teachers daily in the classroom, many of these impasses are beyond pedagogical resources, covering specific areas such as psychology. The proposed theme, which at first may seem outside the line of educational research, is first justified by the Federal Constitution of 1988 when in Art.205 regarding education when it states that the purpose of this should be "the full development of the person". (BRASIL, 1988, Art.205) Corroborated in the Education Guidelines and Bases Law 9,394 of December 20, 1996 in its article 2 "[...] its purpose is the full development of the student" (BRASIL, 1996, Art. .two)

The school, therefore, has the function of promoting this development in the following aspects: physical, psychological, intellectual, social and motor. For this training to be effective, it is not just up to the teacher to go out of his way to develop roles that sometimes go beyond his professional field of activity. It is necessary to involve other professionals who will contribute both to resolving conflicts and to guiding the educator in special cases.

With the general objective of explaining the ways in which the presence of psychologists in the municipality of Cedro-PE has been effective since Law 13.935/2019, and specifically describing the path of Law 13.935/2019 and identifying human resources, activities carried out by Psychology in the municipality of Cedro-PE and point out ways for the implementation of this Law 13,935 in public schools in the municipality of Cedro-PE. Through this study it will be possible to understand the mechanisms adopted by the municipality of Cedro – PE, when it needs to resort to the field of psychology, in addition to detecting these resources in education, we seek to clarify the role of psychology in education as an effective instrument of educational support in the face of demands that are relevant at school.

With this research, it will be possible to understand the reality experienced by the municipality of Cedro in relation to Law 13,935/2019, and based on this knowledge, it is intended that plans and actions will be drawn up aimed at implementing the above Law effectively in Cedrense education. It is therefore clear that such research is extremely important for education and for society as a whole as it seeks to bring everyday school life closer to emerging issues in this field.

The municipality of Cedro in Pernambuco is known as the “Corn Capital”, as agriculture is one of its main sources of income, being one of the largest corn producers in the region. The economy is also driven by “livestock farming, commerce and the provision of services.” (LEITE NETO, 2011, p.47) Cedro from Pernambuco is located in the central hinterland, in a region with a semi-arid climate, with the caatinga being the predominant vegetation. .

According to IBGE (2021), the municipality of Cedro has a population of approximately 11,972 inhabitants, with a school population of 95% aged between 6 and 14 years old according to data from IBGE (2010). Regarding the Human Development Index - HDI, Cedro reached 0.615 (IBGE, 2010). Through this indicator, it is possible to affirm that it is a timid index that needs to improve and grow, for this it is necessary to strengthen public policies in the areas of education, health and income.

By way of comparison, the national HDI in 2018 was 0.759². In comparison with the state of Pernambuco where the HDI is 0.673, Cedro occupies the 47th position among the 185 municipalities that make up the state, in which the highest HDI is 0.788 in Fernando de Noronha and the worst HDI is 0.487 in Manari.

² SOUSA, Rafaela. "Human Development Index (HDI)"; *Brazil School*. Available at: <https://brasile scola.uol.com.br/geografia/idh-indice-desenvolvimento-humano.htm>. Accessed on July 21, 2022.

With only 49 years of political emancipation, Cedro-PE was elevated to the status of municipality on December 20, 1963. (LEITE NETO, 2011) As it is still young, it is also a small city, with only five municipal schools in the urban area and eight schools in rural areas, in addition to two private educational institutions.

There are many phenomena that occur in education, the subjects involved in this process are heterogeneous, each bringing a different perspective on reality. Understanding these historically situated subjects, looking for ways to promote an education that meets the desires of the school and the community, and that in fact includes everyone, is a practice that needs to be more studied, reflected and implemented every day. It is pertinent to highlight, as a finding of this research, the reflection on the means to improve teaching and learning relationships in the school environment.

(...) it can be said that qualitative research has been concerned with the meaning of social phenomena and processes, taking into account motivations, beliefs, values, social representations, which permeate the network of social relationships. (PÁDUA, 2000, p.34)

In this way, we will address the issue within the scope of social research procedures, which deal with subjects in their subjectivities. The method that best translates social research is inductive “In this method, we start by observing facts or phenomena whose causes we want to know. Next, we try to compare them with the aim of discovering the relationships between them.” (GIL, 2008, p. 10-11).

One of the characteristics of social research according to Minayo, Deslandes and Gomes (1994) is that there is an identity between the subject and the object, that is, the researcher identifies with the subjects investigated because he is a human being investigating his fellow man.

This is exploratory research, according to Gil (2008) this type of work “has the main purpose of developing, clarifying and modifying concepts and *ideas*, with a view to formulating more precise problems or researchable hypotheses for subsequent studies.” (p.27, *emphasis added*) Highlighting that this is a topic that still needs to be discussed and deepened for a better understanding and expansion of the presence of psychologists in education.

Field research allows the researcher to delve deeper into theoretical questions, challenging them with real questions, through direct contact with the object studied, “[...] creating knowledge, starting from the reality present in the field.” (MINAYO; DESLANDES; GOMES, 1994, p. 51) Knowledge is full of meaning and meanings, which will bring scientific research increasingly closer to reality. For the authors mentioned above, field research is the

result of the researcher's curiosity and interest in unraveling everyday issues, in order to do so he delves deeper “towards what he wants to know.” (MINAYO; DESLANDES; GOMES, 1994, p.64) There is thus a relationship between the researcher and the field where the former is driven by the concern to unveil the object studied.

According to Minayo, Gomes and Deslandes (1994), interviews can be structured when the *questions are previously formulated* or unstructured when the interviewee speaks freely about the proposed topic. There is also the semi-structured interview where the two forms mentioned are present, “There are forms, however, that articulate these two modalities, characterizing themselves as *semi-structured interviews* .” (MINAYO; DESLANDES; GOMES, 1994, p. 58, *emphasis added*) For this work, this was the chosen form, an articulation between questions that were formulated, and moments in which the interviewees were able to speak freely about the subject in question.

The questions were about the participants' vision of education, their knowledge regarding Law 13,935/2019, how important it is for school education, how this Law was being experienced in the municipality, what activities were being carried out by the psychologist who was working within the scope of school education. It was also discussed the demands and shortcomings in the psychologist's work at the secretariat, her participation in training and planning, case studies and inclusive education. In both interviews the topic of returning to face-to-face classes was quite recurrent and this was the biggest challenge they faced.

Recordings and notes were used to record the speeches, with the consent of the interviewees. The material collected through the interviews was written and brought to the research in its most relevant aspects. The interview is a methodical resource through which the researcher obtains answers from the interviewee to the questions he presents. (LAKATOS and MARCONI, 1992).

The idea of interviewing the Municipal Secretary of Education is justified by the fact that she is the representative of the department in the municipality, and thus we know with more effectiveness and temporal precision the human and technological resources made available to the municipality to ensure the psychologist's performance in education, as well as demands for this area. As defined in the Education Guidelines and Bases Law-LDB of 1996 in Article 11 (BRASIL, 1996), the schools that make up the municipal education network are those for early childhood education: daycare centers and pre-school, and primary education: initial and final years.

The psychologist who works at the Department of Education providing assistance to schools in the municipality was also interviewed. The issue of the reality faced by schools in

the face of demands that encompass knowledge and techniques from the psychological field was approached in a dialogical way.

To obtain the research results, the following instruments were prepared: cover letter, Informed Consent Form (TCLE), which were read by the participants, signed and given a copy of them to each one. At the time of the interview, the participants were asked whether it would be allowed to record the interview, with this feature the conversation it flowed better and it is possible to return to it to review questions and answers. One of the participants agreed and allowed the recording and the other did not.

In research carried out with human beings, there is a consensus on “the importance of informed consent” (GIL, 2008, p.107) in this way, research participants were informed about the objectives of the research, where they had the freedom to participate voluntarily. Respecting the way in which each of the participants chose to participate, both responded to the semi-structured interview in person, in a meeting scheduled in advance, the form of registration was also done in accordance with their consent. Therefore, we obtained permission to record one of the interviewees and made a handwritten record of the other, respecting her freedom of choice and consent.

Electronic recording is the best way to preserve the content of the interview. But it is important to consider that the use of the recorder can only be done with the consent of the interviewee. The disguised use of the recorder constitutes an unjustifiable ethical infraction. If the person, for any reason, does not authorize the recording, it is then necessary to request authorization to take notes. (GIL, 2008, p.119)

Following this prerogative, we recorded the speeches with the consent of each interviewee. We ended both interviews cordially, thus leaving *the door open* in case the questions needed to be explored further. (GIL, 2008)

In the second part, Law 13,935/2019 is discussed and the results of the field research that were carried out through semi-structured interviews with the municipal education department and the psychologist who meets demands in the municipality of Cedro.

LAW 13,935/2019 IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF CEDRO: PROGRESS AND DIFFICULTIES

Teaching and learning are processes that occur through complex phenomena between people of different temperaments, behaviors and subjectivities. In these relational processes, moments arise when the teacher, in his specific pedagogical training, is unable to take care of

everything. Training in psychology, or the presence of a professional in this area at school, can help make the complexity of human beings more understandable for teachers. (SANTOS; GONÇALVES, 2016).

In school spaces, challenges increase daily: inclusion, family disruption, *bullying*, eating disorders, depression, self-mutilation, indiscipline, prejudice, violence, suicide are some examples of the challenges that teachers face in their daily classroom lives. The magnitude of these situations has a very strong impact on the student's psyche, meaning that instead of applying their energy to learning, they spend precious time balancing other emotions. In this sense, when situations fall outside the scope of pedagogy, it is the teacher's and the school's right to seek the help of psychology. The authors Lima *et al.* (2015, p. 02), indicate and guide in this direction. "Referral to psychology is normally made when the school considers that the difficulties presented by students and teachers exceed the possibilities of intervention on a purely pedagogical level".

Not all problems in the classroom can simply be labeled and considered insoluble, there are ways beyond and beyond that can and should be available to both teachers and students and other school staff. These are human and technical resources such as the presence of psychology within the school environment.

Bill 3688/2000 was drafted on this issue, which "provides for the provision of psychology and social services in public basic education networks". This topic generated a broad debate in the Chamber of Deputies and the Federal Senate in the period between the 2000s when the PL was created and 2019 when it finally became Law. In 2019, almost twenty years after the appearance of the first PL 3688/2000, there was greater mobilization on the part of psychology and social service professionals who held conversations and hearings with deputies in order to make them aware of the importance of psychologists and social workers in the school environment. (LAW 13,953/2019, 2020)

Faced with pressure and awareness-raising work, the aforementioned Bill was approved in Congress in 2019, but President Jair Messias Bolsonaro (2018-2022) vetoed it, claiming that it would generate expenses for the government without presenting a form of funding. This decision by President Bolsonaro compromised, in our understanding, the search for solutions to several problems faced by schools, especially public schools. It is important to highlight that in the context of the Bolsonaro government public policies relevant to the nation's intellectual development were put aside as unnecessary. However, the fight continued to be fought by people concerned and committed to education in this country.

The aforementioned President's veto was overturned by Federal Deputies and on December 11, 2019, Law 13,935 was published in the Official Gazette of the Union, which provides for the presence of psychologists and social workers in public schools. Below is Law 13 935/2019 in full:

THE PRESIDENT OF THE REPUBLIC I make it known that the National Congress decrees and I promulgate, in accordance with paragraph 5 of art. 66 of the Federal Constitution, the following Law:

Art. 1 Public basic education networks will have psychology and social services to meet the needs and priorities defined by education policies, through multidisciplinary teams.

§ 1 Multi-professional teams must develop actions to improve the quality of the teaching-learning process, with the participation of the school community, acting in the mediation of social and institutional relationships.

§ 2 The work of the multidisciplinary team must consider the political-pedagogical project of public basic education networks and their educational establishments.

Art. 2 Education systems will have 1 (one) year, from the date of publication of this Law, to take the necessary measures to comply with its provisions.

Art. 3 This Law comes into force on the date of its publication.

Brasília, December 11, 2019; 198th of Independence and 131st of the Republic.

JAIR MESSIAS BOLSONARO

Law 13 935/2019, as we can see, is very straightforward, it establishes the presence of psychologists and social workers in public schools, but it does not describe how this should happen, it only stipulates from when compliance should begin as positive legislation. The deadline is one year after its promulgation, that is, from December 2020.

With the Covid-19 pandemic that began in March 2020, this issue ended up being forgotten. Most schools adopted remote teaching as a way of maintaining contact with students due to the social isolation imposed by the pandemic. This same class format continued in 2021.

After progress in vaccination, it was possible for some sectors to return to face-to-face activities, schools, however, actually returned in 2022. In this face-to-face return, after all the challenges imposed by the pandemic, schools encountered several difficulties, several problems were aggravated and the presence of psychologists (those) and social workers has become even more urgent.

The Federal Council of Psychology (CFP), together with the Federal Council of Social Service (CFESS) and the Union of Municipal Education Directors (UNDIME), met to debate the regulation of Law 13,935/2019, in order to “avoid distortions between the areas of activity of these professionals.” (LAW 13,953/2019, 2020). The debate around this standardization has continued and expanded to other entities such as: National Council of Education Secretaries -

Consed, the National Front of Mayors - FNP, and the Brazilian Association of Municipalities - ABM.

The research participants, as previously mentioned, were the municipal secretary of education and the psychologist who meets the demands of the municipality. Next, the results of the interviews are presented. The focus is to find out their perception of the role and importance of the psychologist's support at school, especially during this period of return to face-to-face classes after the COVID-19 pandemic.

The perception of the manager of the Department of Education

The interview with the Municipal Secretary of Education of the municipality of Cedro took place in the department itself, she has a degree in pedagogy and a specialization in Biology, working as a teacher in the final years of elementary school, with 30 years of experience in education, she has worked as a pedagogical coordinator and also as director. According to De Oliveira, Libâneo & Toschi (2012) "Organization and management are means to achieve the purposes of teaching." (p.420) it is in this aspect that we seek to dialogue with the education department through the municipal body that is responsible for "[...]make schools work[...]" The responsibility of the Municipal Department of Education is extremely great, given this it would not be possible to understand the reality of the municipality's schools, in relation to Law 13,953/2019, without first having spoken to the legal representative of the Department of Education.

For her, the classroom is a place of learning for both the students and the teacher, which is why she enjoys teaching because she learns from the students. However, he highlighted that it is important for the teacher to be well in all aspects, especially in terms of health. "*When the teacher is well, it is wonderful to be in the classroom, but there are days when he is not so well* ." (SECRETARY)

We want to highlight two points in this speech: the first concerns the teaching-learning process, for this two-way learning relationship to happen it is necessary to understand that the student is not a mere object of learning but is rather an active subject who produces knowledge. Having this vision, it is possible to move beyond banking education to a democratic education that forms critical and reflective citizens. "Whoever teaches learns by teaching and whoever learns teaches by learning." (FREIRE, 1996, sn)

The second point is a reflection on the working conditions given to the teacher, we bring back Paulo Freire (1991) in the interview given to the science notebook. He gave a blunt and

sincere answer when answering the question “Why is the quality of education in the country so bad?” He responded that one of the issues that directly influences is “ [...] the lack of dignity in the treatment of teaching staff.” (FREIRE, 1991, p.20) Thus he lists a series of minimum conditions that can provide improvements for teachers, among them are: the salary issue, workload that provides time for the teacher to study and plan in addition to continuing education.

The secretary stated that it is extremely important for the appreciation of ethical and moral principles, that education provides young people with a dignified entry into the world of work. The Federal Constitution of 1988, in Article 205, recommends training for citizenship and qualification for work as the main function of education. (BRASIL, 1988)

More broadly, the role of education is much more comprehensive, having a function of humanizing the person, allowing them to appropriate what has been historically produced by humanity, “We thus have the social function of education, responsible for enabling individuals to appropriation of the knowledge, skills and values necessary to become members of the human race.” (FACCI; LEONARDO; SOUZA, 2019, p. 76)

He was asked how inclusive education happened. She informed us that students with disabilities are enrolled in regular education, the municipality selected caregivers with the minimum requirement of completing high school. The Specialized Service room is being restructured with the replacement of materials.

The perception of the Psychologist who works at schools in the municipality

The psychologist who works at the Department of Education was a teacher for 27 years, after retiring she sought to fulfill her desire to work in the health sector by identifying with psychology. She completed her training as a psychologist in 2012 and has been working in this area since then, working in various places such as: psychiatric hospital, Social Assistance Reference Center (CRAS), in schools and in the office.

Regarding the social function of the school, she highlighted that the school “ *is the space where citizens seek knowledge for their growth as a whole.* ”(PSYCHOLOGIST) A very well-crafted sentence, but we need to understand that this is all, speaking of integral education, that is, in the sense of complete training Facci, Leonardo and Souza (2019) state that “any obstacle to the appropriation of generic heritage is obstacle to the full development of the individual as a fully human being.” (FACCI; LEONARDO; SOUZA, 2019, p. 77)

We thus realize that the vision of education presented by the participants is still at the level of naive consciousness (FREIRE, 1997), as it does not question the *status quo* imposed on education of the popular classes. Both statements were restricted to perceiving education as preparation for work, and life in society as it is, conforming to the same.

In a critical vision of education “The professional must expand his knowledge about man, his way of being in the world, replacing with a critical vision the naive vision of reality, deformed by narrow specialisms.” (FREIRE, 1997, p.16) for this reason, the objective of school education, especially for the working class, must be questioned and problematized. What is the real role of education in a society divided into antagonistic and unequal social classes? Education is what most of the time prepares the less favored class simply to serve as cheap labor, who will perform tasks without reflection, simply corresponding to the social expectations that have been imposed on them since school education.

Educational practice, therefore, is an integral part of the dynamics of social relations, of the forms of social organization. Its purposes and processes are determined by antagonistic interests of social classes. In teaching work, being a manifestation of educational practice, interests of all kinds are present - social, political, economic, cultural - which need to be understood by teachers. (LIBÂNEO, 2017, p.27)

It is the function of school education, especially in public schools that belong to the popular classes, to form critical citizens, aware of all the oppression and exploitation imposed on workers, who produce goods but cannot, in most cases, enjoy them. The full development of human beings can only happen in their entirety when they have access to the goods produced by humanity in both the material and immaterial field.

In capitalist society, where natural equality between individuals is proclaimed, it is assumed that education should provide everyone with comprehensive training, however, when this does not happen, the causes of this failure are sought in the individual himself and not in the capitalist economic structure. which, by having capital as its matrix, establishes relationships of exploitation, domination and inequality. (FACCI; LEONARDO; SOUZA, 2019, p. 78)

What we have tried to make clear from the beginning of this work is exactly how the school results of the popular classes are interpreted, often without taking into account the inequality of access to material and immaterial goods. To avoid falling into the meritocracy discourse, it is necessary to always remember that social, political, economic and cultural aspects are directly linked to the results achieved both by students and by the school itself.

She highlighted that unfortunately LAW 13,935/2019 is still on paper, there are few public schools that have the presence of a psychologist and social worker. She brought up the

reflection that schools recognize this need and that having at least one psychologist in the Department of Education, as is the case with Cedro, is already a good sign, however it is just a drop of water in the ocean of needs. For this Law, which is a dream, to become effective, she stated that it is necessary to demand from the competent authorities compliance with this policy and others that guarantee the right to quality public education.

As the psychologist spoke about her work at the secretariat, it was possible to see that she knows the technical references for the work of psychologists in basic education. She acknowledged that she had already read the document but it had been some time ago. She revealed that she participates in teacher planning and training because she believes it is a moment of important pedagogical discussion where the psychologist's contributions are necessary. According to her, as her work is at the Department of Education, as schools request her intervention, she will have access to the Pedagogical Political Projects of each one. There are also mini projects that are those created based on the school's PPP. When these institutions are developing this type of activity, they ask for your help, so that they can analyze and see how the psychologist's perspective can contribute.

Still talking about the demands, she was asked if, as a psychologist at the Municipal Department of Education, she had a support network and how referrals happen when necessary.

She responded that there is a team at the secretariat that monitors the most aggravating cases, when psychotherapy is necessary, they are referred to the health secretariat. Referrals are also made for tutoring. In both situations, the team studies the situation and talks to the student's family before making the referrals.

There was also talk about the impact of returning to face-to-face classes after two years of remote teaching, where many children did not have access, others never went to the school's physical space. She reflected that children and adolescents were kept away not only from school, but also from other social groups such as: church, squares and even their own families. According to his words: *“So what happened, the school left the school and went indoors, a very big impact. Many parents didn't even have the knowledge of technology to work with their child, organize a cell phone, a notebook, most didn't even have one, they didn't even have access.”*(PSYCHOLOGIST)

This was unfortunately the reality of thousands of Brazilian children during these two years of the pandemic in the educational scenario, according to data from the technical note “Distance learning in basic education in the face of the Covid-19 pandemic” prepared by the “All for Education” movement (April 2020), 67% of Brazilian households had internet access,

of which 99% were in class A, 94% in class B, 76% in class C and 40% in class D and E. (EDUCAÇÃO, 2020)

Considering also that the most used device for this access was the cell phone present in 93% of households, 100% in class A and 84% in classes D and E. The computer was present in 42% of households, 47% in class C and 9% in classes D and E. When presenting this data, the document warned about the existing educational disparities and how this inequality in access to the internet and adequate technological equipment was essential for the implementation of remote teaching, and that the lack of them could further aggravate this situation, penalizing “even more those in more vulnerable situations.” (EDUCAÇÃO, 2020, p.9)

The Network Literacy survey also found that “[...] the remote classroom, in this pandemic, is reduced to the cell phone screen connected to the WhatsApp application for 71.58% of teachers, which is an indication of the precariousness of conditions for virtual connectivity for teachers and students.” (DEL PINO, 2020, p. 192) . This situation has left a large gap in the learning of children and adolescents, the next few years will be a challenge for the recovery of learning.

The pandemic crisis took place within this context, in which the suspension of daily school attendance represented, for a large part of poor school segments, the suppression of the only or main mediation they had with the practices and knowledge necessary for school learning.” (OLIVEIRA; ALGEBAILLE, 2021, p.212-213)

From the data presented, it was possible to see that the vast majority of Brazilian families were not prepared for remote education, and that the aggravating factors left by this period fell mainly on the popular classes who already face a series of difficulties in the schooling process.

Also reported on the interview carried out with the psychologist from the Municipal Department of Education of Cedro-PE, she mentioned the National Common Curricular Base - BNCC, which addresses socio-emotional skills as a way of preparing the student beyond purely cognitive knowledge. According to our interviewee, this proposal is important because there are many children and adolescents who do not accept themselves, do not love themselves, and do not accept their families. It is necessary to work on what she called self: self-care, self-love, self-understanding. To get along well with others you need to get along well with yourself.

In this training perspective, the aim is to form the human being in its entirety “ *We need to imagine myself first, first I need to take care of myself, know myself and love myself, so that*

we can happen and then the planet.” This is an emancipatory education that prepares the subject for relationships with the whole, with oneself, with the collective and with the planet itself.

The interview ended with her report on how her career as a teacher added her psychology work to education, in her speech she brought up the struggle that is a teaching career, and how she feels pleasure in the profession she pursues today because the most valuable thing is to help the human being.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Thus, it is considered from the reading and discussion of the concepts and meanings pointed out by the authors who collaborated in the perspective of this work, that psychology is a complementary field to the field of school education. The initiative points to an analysis that suggests that the presence of professionals in the areas of psychology is increasingly necessary in the school space given the complexity of society and its impetuous transformations. It was realized that psychology is necessary in the educational field and that the presence of psychologists in public schools became even more important after the pandemic.

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